

Cultural Narratives of Conejo Valley: Exploring the Lived Experiences of Conejo Valley Residents: A Comprehensive Study of Social Interactions, Environmental Engagement, and Suburban Lifestyle in Southern California

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ABSTRACT

With the use of 50 interviews with adult residents within the suburb of Southern California, Conejo Valley, the study seeks to learn how people relate to the social environment and structure. The questionnaire used in administering the question to the participants contained eight questions in a close-ended format. Interview questions addressed matters of transportation behavior, recreational activity, length of stay, intensity of outdoor behavior, and the attitude toward regional amenities, weather, and the general quality of life. The data was collected using in-person interaction with participants as it allowed for observation of not only their oral responses but also non-verbal communications. Thematic analysis with a grounded theory perspective was used to extract patterns within the responses, and a comparative investigation was conducted to assess potential correlations between socio-demographic factors (for example, age or duration of residency) and lifestyle factors. Informed consent and privacy ethical safeguards were followed at each step of data collection. This research contributes to knowledge about suburban life through a critical examination of the way of life, social processes, and environmental factors that affect people's experiences in Conejo Valley.

INTRODUCTION

Suburban living is usually characterized by a sense of community, closeness to nature, and certain lifestyle choices that separate it from urban and rural living (Creanza, Kolodny, and Feldman 2017). Conejo Valley, a Southern California suburban community is the case study chosen to understand the complexities of suburban life. Located in Ventura County and encompassing such cities as Thousand Oaks, Westlake Village, and Agoura Hills, Conejo Valley has evolved from a farming community to a very developed suburb with a high quality of life

(Creanza, Kolodny, and Feldman 2017). Conejo Valley is a microcosm of broader suburban trends and therefore presents an ideal location for exploring the intricacies of suburban living.

This research seeks to provide a comprehensive image of suburban life in Conejo Valley by way of examining the intersectionality of environmental engagement, social relations, socioeconomic status, and cultural diversity. From this research, there will be an increased understanding of how residents engage with their environment, their neighborhood, and the advantages and disadvantages of suburban living. Using adult residents' responses, this research seeks to target the realities of suburban life with the ultimate goal of generalizability to the broader population of Conejo Valley.

OBJECTIVES

Through my research, I aim to find an understanding of the lifestyle, cultural dynamics, and community perceptions of adult residents in Conejo Valley. I conducted 50 interviews with residents of Conejo Valley outside of a grocery store to gather the data. These interviews were geared towards understanding how people relate to their environment and what affects these people's daily lives. The ten questions include modes of transportation, duration of residency, outdoor activities, and overall livability to assess how the built and natural environment shapes the social behavior of Conejo Valley residents. Primarily, I am trying to find out in what way the lifestyle and perception of local services of the residents affect the community experience in Conejo Valley.

METHODS

Demographic variability for age and gender was ensured through stratified sampling. Data was collected with a standardized questionnaire consisting of ten close-ended questions, which are focused on leisure activities, mode of transportation, residency period, level of outdoor activity, and general locality friendliness including amenities, weather, and livability. Collection of data was done directly to better understand the rationale behind respondents' answers by observing how they spoke and their body language. A thematic analysis will be used to analyze the interviews through a grounded theory approach to determine patterns found in the data.

Furthermore, this research will employ comparative research to find possible relationships between some socio-demographic variables such as age or period of residency and important lifestyle factors. Every participant provided consent, and all confidentiality measures will be kept at all stages of the research analysis. The results from this research will add to the field of anthropology by explaining how lifestyle choices of community members interact with the built and natural environment and by providing an explanation of social phenomena within the boundaries of anthropological theories.

RESULTS

Question 1: Where do you usually spend your free time?

- A) Library
- B) Home
- C) Park
- D) Cafe
- E) Other

A person's personality, attitude, and abilities shape their engagement in leisure activities. Leisure choice is mainly based on age, gender, income, and local culture. Those with higher incomes have a greater variety of leisure activities. The concept of free time is primarily a characteristic of post-industrial societies. The United States is an example of a post-industrial society because it has passed the stage where the economy shifts from a manufacturing-focused economy to a service-based one (Dridea and Sztruten n.d.). For most people, leisure remains time free of obligations. Free time is the time left after work and school requirements and family and household obligations (Zuzanek 1970).

Based on the responses that I gathered from the question above, 33 out of the 50 Conejo Valley residents chose "Home" and the rest (17) selected "Other" as their main places to spend their free time. Most respondents being at home during leisure time suggests a local cultural preference for family-centric lifestyles (Dridea and Sztruten n.d.). Given that Conejo Valley is a suburban area, it can be inferred that close-knit familial relationships are valued above social community gatherings (Shaw 2018). Home environments can be customized to fit personal

preferences and do not have the social pressures in public spaces. Social pressures can include behaving a certain way or dressing appropriately (Zuzanek 1970). The preference for home could also indicate a national cultural shift towards more insular lifestyles post-pandemic. Because many people have become accustomed to being at home, they may have developed a preference for private environments. The rest of the respondents chose "Other", however, I chose to not inquire about the specific location because it might be private. Their choice could either reflect a preference for private spaces outside of the home or places outside traditional public spaces. It may indicate that a significant number of Conejo Valley residents prefer niche spaces that serve specific personal needs (Shaw 2018). Based on my findings, it seems that residents of the Conejo Valley are inclined towards more introverted leisure activities. Through my observations during ethnographic fieldwork, I can confirm that public social spaces, such as parks, are less frequently used in Conejo Valley (Shaw 2018).

Question 2. Transportation - Do you mostly:

- A) Drive
- B) Walk
- C) Bike
- D) Bus

Transportation is influenced by economic, geographical, cultural, and political factors (Brar 2005).

For the second question, 48 out of the 50 participants prefer driving as their primary mode of transportation, while 2 out of the 50 individuals opt for walking. Conejo Valley, located in a suburban region of Southern California, has sprawling neighborhoods that would necessitate the use of automobiles, as destinations are separated by distances that exceed comfortable walking limits (Medina, Lois González, and Somoza Medina 2022). Automobiles were created in the late 19th century (Brar 2005). The dominance of driving can be largely attributed to the built environment. Urban planning in Conejo Valley appears to prioritize road networks and automobile access over pedestrian infrastructure. Cars are an efficient way to cover longer distances and manage busy lifestyles. Owning and driving a car is a marker of economic success.

Suburban planning policies historically have favored road construction and highway development over walkability and public transit.

While the overwhelming majority choose to drive, the two respondents reported walking. Walking is the most common method of commuting for humans until the phenomenon of urban sprawl arrived. The technology development on motorised vehicles has successfully replaced walking amongst the citizens (Nuzir and Dewancker 2016). Their choice might be influenced by a desire for physical activity and a healthier lifestyle, an awareness of and commitment to reducing one's carbon footprint, and living in parts of Conejo Valley where essential services (e.g., local shops, parks, or community centers) are within walking distance. Even if some individuals prefer more sustainable or healthier options, the surrounding environment may limit their ability to act on those preferences (Buerglener 2008). As a bipedal mammal, walking is innate to humans and has evolved into a social and cultural activity (Pucher and Buehler 2010). The healthiest modes of transportation in cities are walking and bicycling, which give people regular opportunities for beneficial physical activity. Walking and biking generate indirect public health benefits by reducing the use of automobiles, thus diminishing air, water, and noise pollution and the overall level of traffic danger (Middleton 2011). There are several reasons for promoting increased cycling and walking (Nuzir and Dewancker 2016). They use much fewer non-renewable resources than any motorized method of transportation and produce almost no noise or air pollution (Middleton 2011). The traveler directly supplies the energy needed for walking and cycling, and the act of using that energy provides beneficial cardiovascular workout (Nuzir and Dewancker 2016). Only a small portion of the space required for car use and parking is used for walking and bicycling (Buerglener 2008). Furthermore, both in terms of direct user expenditure and public infrastructure investment, walking and bicycling are cost-effective options that are significantly less expensive than private vehicles and public transportation (Nuzir and Dewancker 2016).

Question 3: How long have you lived in Conejo Valley?

- A) Less than 1 year
- B) 1–5 years
- C) 5–10 years
- D) More than 10 years

Remarkably, every respondent indicated that they have lived in Conejo Valley for more than 10 years. There was no variability in the answer responses for Question 3 (Stedman 1999). This suggests a strong pattern of long-term residency, stability, and community attachment. Perhaps the most significant implication of this result is the apparent lack of transient populations in Conejo Valley (Stedman 1999). This trend is possibly motivated by economic security, standard of living, and social harmony. Long-term residence would also be most likely to be associated with stable social networks, neighborhood familiarity, and ongoing investment in local institutions, such as schools, businesses, and residential associations. Socioculturally, long-standing residents of a location are more likely to engage in cultural events, community events, and local politics (Stedman 1999).

Such stability can be the result of a preference for home ownership over rented properties, the zoning laws preventing new development, or a long-term presence-based economy at a local level via stable employment and quality services. Another effect of long-term presence is the intensification of local norms and values. Strong-stability societies have strong collective identities that affect cultural expectations, social conduct, and political beliefs (Stedman 1999).

If new residents are not common, then dominant social norms established by long-time residents can persist with little external influence, resulting in a relatively homogeneous cultural setting. This has social inclusion implications, since long-time resident communities may be less able or less inclined to accommodate change or less likely to accept new residents with other backgrounds and perspectives (Stedman 1999).

Companies in Conejo Valley can have a stable consumer base, allowing for sustained local economic activity and reduced market volatility. Local enterprises catering to long-time residents can enjoy long-term customer loyalty (Stedman 1999). Another consideration is the extent to which long-term residence helps to ensure intergenerational continuity. Intergenerational continuity can assist in ensuring the transmission of cultural knowledge and local customs, which can assist in the perpetuation of a shared sense of identity across generations (Stedman 1999). Such communities that experience small numbers of new residents coming in will struggle to adopt new ideas, leading to a slow pace of social, cultural, and economic practice change (Stedman 1999).

Question 4: How often do you go outdoors?

- A) Every day
- B) A few times a week
- C) Once in a while
- D) Never

The majority, 38 out of the 50, reported going outside daily, 10 participants reported going outside a few times a week, and the remaining 2 individuals reported going outside from time to time. This high rate of outdoor activity could be explained by various reasons from lifestyle, school or work timetables, accessibility of outdoor spaces, or social and cultural needs for frequent outdoor activity. That there were no entries for the "Never" category indicates that Conejo Valley residents make the outdoors a part of their lives to some extent. No respondent is entirely unconnected from outdoor spaces, which may speak to a widespread cultural or environmental assumption that being outdoors is a normal part of everyday life in Conejo Valley. Regular outdoor engagement has been associated with a wide variety of physical and mental health benefits, such as better cardiovascular health, better mood management, and less stress and anxiety.

Green places offer human social and health benefits (Jordan, Sorensen, and Clark 2015). Previous studies have shown that direct contact with nature is highly beneficial for human beings (Lee, Min, and Ohno 2012). Green spaces have been linked to higher community satisfaction, reduced stress levels, less irritability, more patience, and joy, and a longer attention span. In addition, natural components encourage the utilization of outdoor spaces, which is critical in inner-city neighborhoods (Lee, Min, and Ohno 2012). Public green spaces allow community members to interact with the outdoors (Jordan, Sorensen, and Clark 2015). Natural settings also promote social relationships (Lee, Min, and Ohno 2012). Experiencing natural environments through direct use helps people make sense of a place, including developing psychological attachments, cognitions associated with the place, and a sense of social belonging (Lee, Min, and Ohno 2012). Green spaces are generally underutilized, with only one-fifth of the US population participating in sports and recreation activities (Jordan, Sorensen, and Clark 2015). High engagement outdoors may indicate that the participants live in an environment conducive to and encouraging outdoor time, either by way of access to parks, walkable infrastructure, or favorable

weather (Biglieri 2021). The 10% of respondents who said they go outdoors only sometimes may just like being indoors (Pyky et al. 2018). My findings may be reflective of planning that encourages outdoor mobility, a climate conducive to being outside (see Question 6 results for further information), or an overall acknowledgment of the benefits of being outside. The fact that there is a high degree of outdoor activity suggests a demand for well-maintained parks, pedestrian-friendly areas, and outdoor recreational facilities (Biglieri 2021). The high level of daily outdoor activity can also be indicative of a society that places a high premium on health and activity, either through formal exercise routines, social outdoor pursuits, or work-related obligations requiring outdoor presence (Pyky et al. 2018). The survey findings of high levels of outdoor activity can also imply potential economic benefits, as frequent outdoor activity is more likely to lead to high levels of patronage for local businesses such as cafés and farmers' markets (Pyky et al. 2018). The findings also indicate social benefit potential because outdoor recreation has the potential to bring about a sense of community by providing venues for social contact in shared spaces such as parks. Policymakers and planners can use this information to justify public investment in public outdoor areas (Biglieri 2021).

Question 5: Do you think Conejo Valley is a good place for pets?

- A) Yes
- B) No
- C) I don't know

An overwhelming 47 out of 50 chose that Conejo Valley is a good place for pets. When asked what they gain out of their interactions with pets, most pet owners say companionship and the urge to love and care for another being (Herzog 2011, 237). This majority suggests a broadly shared perception that the region offers a pet-friendly environment, likely influenced by factors such as abundant green spaces, pet-oriented infrastructure, and local policies that facilitate pet ownership (Franti, Kraus, and Borhani 1974). The concept that living with an animal can increase human health, psychological well-being, and lifespan is known as the "pet effect" (Herzog 2011, 236).

The 3 out of the 50 respondents replied "No." A respondent initially said "Yes" but, after a pause of a few seconds, reversed his answer to "No" with additional clarification and stated that

Conejo Valley is pet-friendly for dogs but not for cats in an apartment in his opinion. This suggests a division in pet-friendliness perceptions between those who are in apartments and may experience more restrictions in contrast to single-family homes. This respondent who dissented from the majority that Conejo Valley is pet-friendly illustrates how further deliberation and contextual analysis is important (Franti, Kraus, and Borhani 1974).

In the United States, more than two-thirds of homes have a pet whom they consider to be family members (Herzog 2011, 237). Pet ownership has become a popular cultural phenomenon (Herzog 2011, 238). The results are in line with broader suburban American trends, where pet ownership is widely regarded as a positive component of family life and community values.

The general results of this survey question indicate that Conejo Valley is a pet-friendly environment.

Question 6: Do you like the weather in Conejo Valley?

Yes

No

Sometimes

All respondents unanimously answered "Yes" to Question 6. I chose to include this question in the questionnaire to understand how environmental factors such as weather affect other aspects of life, and long-term residency decisions (see Question 3). Weather is a crucial determinant of an area's livability (Skinner 2019). Conejo Valley has a warm climate, with mild, wet winters and hot, dry summers, and is a better place to live compared to places that experience harsher weather conditions (Lundberg, Komarovskiy, and McInerney 2019). Satisfaction with the weather goes hand in hand with a lifestyle that enjoys outdoor pursuits (see Question 4), such as hiking, biking, and other recreational pursuits offered in the numerous parks and trails of the valley (Skinner 2019).

Further, the absence of any "No" or "Sometimes" responses shows the absence of serious weather conditions like extreme heat or cold found in other areas of the United States (Lundberg, Komarovskiy, and McInerney 2019). The uniformity of the respondent's answers may suggest that Conejo Valley residents have adapted to living well with the climate or individuals who do not

like the climate have moved away, thus becoming a self-selection bias in which only the individuals who prefer the climate remain in the region (Skinner 2019).

Studies have shown that consistent exposure to favorable weather can improve mood, reduce stress, and promote overall health. The presence of high temperatures further contributes to a climate conducive to physical and psychological well-being (Lundberg, Komarovskiy, and McNerny 2019). The generalized positive response might be a function not only of the objective merits of the weather but also of the psychological and emotional gains gained by inhabitants residing in Conejo Valley with pleasing weather all year round (Skinner 2019).

Question 7: Do you like living in Conejo Valley?

- A) Yes
- B) It's ok
- C) No
- D) I don't know

All the respondents answered "Yes" to Question 7. While the survey contained a range of questions related to satisfaction in Conejo Valley, Question 7 directly asked the respondents whether they were content with residing in the region. The results of Question 7 could be an indication that the region has succeeded in providing a high standard of living for the residents. There was a dramatic shift of the American population to the suburbs in the post-WWII period suggests suburban living may have advantages (Morris, 2019). Their responses may imply that the community is meeting the expectations of its people. As a suburban community, the Conejo Valley enjoys many benefits, such as good schools, safe neighborhoods, and recreation centers. These are likely contributing factors to the happiness of the people, and the repetition of the response means that the community is successfully providing for these basic needs. Conejo Valley has mid-to-high average family incomes, an educated populace, and relatively low unemployment (Morris, 2019). These socio-economic factors play a significant part in shaping the overall perception of the area. Higher-income residents who have secure employment are most likely to be content with their way of living because they can access amenities and services that suit their needs (Morris, 2019).

The physical environment of the area determines how individuals think about it (see Question 4). The climate, which is largely nice and warm throughout the year, also makes the area look beautiful. The absence of extreme weather or environmental hazards, such as frequent natural disasters, may also contribute to the general feeling of security and happiness in the community (see Question 6). People who live in places with pleasant landscapes tend to have greater life satisfaction, which could be the reason for their good attitude toward living in the area (Morris, 2019). The positive sentiment expressed through the survey shows that there may be an active and engaged community that contributes to creating and sustaining the quality of life in the area (Morris, 2019).

Question 8: Do you think that Conejo Valley is a good place to visit for tourists?

- A) Yes
- B) It's okay
- C) No
- D) I don't know

Out of the 50 responses, 41 participants said that Conejo Valley is a good place to visit for tourists, while 6 considered it to be an okay destination, and 3 stated that it is not a good vacation destination.

The overwhelming majority who viewed Conejo Valley positively as a tourist destination, 41 out of 50 respondents, is indicative of overall satisfaction with the area's attributes. Conejo Valley offers a peaceful, suburban alternative to the hustle and bustle of urban cities, shaping their opinion that Conejo Valley is an inviting place for tourists seeking a quieter retreat. Also, the trends in the answers may indicate a feeling of pride in the community (Chick, 2009). Most residents probably equate the area with personal or family-friendly experiences and feel that the visitors would also appreciate the surroundings (Chick, 2018).

The 6 respondents who considered Conejo Valley as an "okay" tourist destination may have considered the appeal of the area as a relatively limited tourist destination in California. This group may be individuals who feel that the area lacks some of the attractions or activities that would draw large numbers of tourists (Chick, 2018). Conejo Valley does not have the profile for the same world-famous tourist destinations that neighboring cities such as Los Angeles, Santa

Barbara, or Malibu have (Chick, 2009). These neighboring cities are most likely to view the area as being overshadowed by these proximate neighboring cities, where there are famous sites and entertainment venues. Their response proposes that even though Conejo Valley may be considered the best location for those who seek nature and peace, it cannot be considered the best destination for those tourists who look for a diversity of experiences (Chick, 2018).

The 3 individuals who said Conejo Valley is not a good tourist destination are a minority belief in the survey. The group might perceive that the location is missing specific amenities, facilities, or features that would cater to a tourist economy. Such individuals might have directly experienced the constraints of the region, especially if they consider it to favor locals over tourists. These findings suggest that Conejo Valley is not necessarily a tourist spot in the traditional sense, but it does have a certain kind of appeal that can attract particular kinds of tourists (Chick, 2009). By building on its positives and addressing problems from locals as well as potential tourists, Conejo Valley can continue to retain its charm while establishing a sustainable tourism industry (Chick, 2018).

CONCLUDING STATEMENT

These are indications of Conejo Valley's probable car dependency, long residential patterns, high outdoor frequency, and the prevalent notion of the area as being pet-friendly. Car and house prevalence is probably an indication of the suburban culture of concern for individual space and freedom of mobility. By using the case study of Conejo Valley, this research enhances knowledge of suburban living and its applicability to the national discourse on suburban culture. While cars provide residents with their desired mobility, future research could examine the economic and environmental costs of such dependence in Conejo Valley, as well as potential alternatives in the form of improved public transit or pedestrian-friendly suburban planning. Further research may investigate the nature of the "Other" spaces to which people migrate and whether there are more emerging patterns in the manner community residents engage in free time.

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